

Socio-economic factors affecting the distribution of marine litter: The Portuguese case study

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ABSTRACT

Marine litter is a growing global problem with serious environmental, economic, social, and health threats. Understanding the socio-economic factors that influence the types and amounts of litter is of utmost importance. In this study, an integrative analysis of the socio-economic factors that characterize the beach litter distribution in continental Portugal and the Azores archipelago was conducted via a cluster analysis, implementing a novel technique to support the difficult task of marine litter characterization. The results highlighted that the most abundant beach litter material is plastic (92.9 %), followed by paper (2.2 %), wood (1.5 %), and metal (1.3 %). The majority of the items could not be attributed to a specific source (46.5 %). The remaining were attributed to public litter (34.5 % of total aggregated items), fishing (9.8 %), sewage-related debris (6.4 %) and shipping (2.2 %). The top-three beach litter categories were small plastic pieces (0–2.5 cm, 43.5 %), cigarette butts (30.1 %), and medium plastic pieces (2.5–50 cm, 26.4 %). A positive relation between both municipality environment expenditures and population density and the quantity and typology of litter was found. Beach litter quantity and categories were also associated with specific economic sectors, as well as with geographical/hydrodynamic conditions, demonstrating the utility of the technique and its applicability to other regions.

1. Introduction

Marine litter can be defined as “any persistent solid material discarded, manufactured or processed, disposed of, abandoned, or lost in the marine and coastal environment” (UNEP, 2021). It consists of items that are accidentally or deliberately discarded directly in the coastal and marine environment or are brought into it by rivers, sewage, stormwater, or wind (Galgani et al., 2010). Higher abundances can be found around the main shipping routes and in coastal waters near urbanized regions. The litter items can be found floating, suspended at different depths or deposited on the coast or on the sea floor (Galgani et al., 2010; Sá et al., 2016).

Marine litter is originated from a variety of sources, most of which are land-based. These include recreational use of the coast, diffuse public littering, industry, harbors, non-sanitary landfills and illegal dumpsites, sewage overflows, and losses from waste collection, sorting

and transport (UNEP, 2005). Land-generated litter can be transported by wind, rain, and waterways to the ocean and water level variations, e.g. due to tides and storms, mobilize and wash off litter from coastlines and estuarine areas (Erüz et al., 2023; Terzi et al., 2020). These transport mechanisms can be exacerbated by extreme weather events (Neves et al., 2015). Maritime sources include commercial shipping, ferries, fishing activities, recreational vessels, military and research fleets, offshore installations and platforms (aquaculture and offshore oil and gas platforms), legal, illegal or accidental dumping at sea, and the wear and tear of the implanted equipment (Galgani et al., 2015; Mordecai et al., 2011; Martins et al., 2020).

Marine litter is composed of a wide variety of materials, with plastic as the most abundant. Due to its characteristics, plastic can be easily transported far from its origin, being considered the most difficult type of debris to control and identify the original source (Andrady and Neal, 2009; Azwifarwi and Lasiak, 1997; Erüz and Ozseker, 2021). According

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to Hsu et al. (2021), in 2016, the total virgin plastic polymers and fibers production in Europe amounted to 66,786 thousand tones, and 37,068 thousand tons of plastic waste was generated. The majority of losses to the environment occur at the waste generation phase (total of 3393 thousand tones), while roughly half of the total plastic waste generated went through non-circular treatment (e.g. landfilling, incineration) and exports.

The impact of litter on the marine environment is wide-ranging. It can cause physical damage to marine wildlife through entanglement or ingestion (Guerrero-Meseguer et al., 2020; Kühn et al., 2015; Gall and Thompson, 2015; Guerrero-Meseguer et al., 2020; Kühn et al., 2015; Sá et al., 2016), and as a vector of various invasive species (Guerrero-Meseguer et al., 2020; Kühn et al., 2015; Molnar et al., 2008; Gall and Thompson, 2015; Rochman et al., 2013). Under certain physical and chemical conditions, marine litter, especially plastics, have the ability to adsorb different organic and inorganic matter (Alberghini et al., 2023), which can lead to the introduction of toxic chemicals into the marine food webs (Trouwborst, 2011). Among the aesthetical effects of beach pollution and the reduction of water quality that affect human/ecosystems health and tourism, marine litter also poses a navigational hazard to ships. The economic impact is also significant, with estimated reductions in the GDP in the order of billions of dollars, due to the loss in revenue from tourism, fishing, aquaculture, clean-up costs, and others (Josse, 2021; Lupiac, 2022; WWF, 2021; Gall and Thompson, 2015; Mouat et al., 2010).

Marine litter is one of today's major environmental concerns. This problem was first highlighted during the 70s (Carpenter and Smith, 1972; Carpenter et al., 1972), but only a few decades later it gained considerable attention at the political level (Ryan, 2015). In recent years, marine litter has become a priority of national and international agendas (González-Fernández et al., 2021; UNEP, 2016). Many regions of the world have adopted Action Plans, such as OSPAR, HELCOM, and Barcelona Convention in Europe. At the global level, target 14.1 of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) focuses on marine litter, while more recently, a legally binding global agreement on plastic pollution was endorsed at the fifth session of the United Nations Environmental Assembly (UNEA 5.2) (Sun et al., 2021). In Europe, marine litter is explicitly addressed by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), but there are many other policies deal with plastic and waste across the whole life cycle of items that are often found on beaches and in the sea, namely the Single-Use Plastics Directive, the Waste Framework Directive, and the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive. Efforts towards harmonized marine litter monitoring have been driven by OSPAR and the MSFD Common Implementation Strategy (OSPAR, 2010; Galgani et al., 2013), enabling the comparison across countries and regions, and establishing baselines and thresholds for beach litter at the EU level (van Loon et al., 2020; Hanke et al., 2019).

Despite those initiatives, there is no single or easy solutions to this problem. Prevention is the most effective approach and this requires a concerted effort from local to international societal sectors, from regulatory and economic instruments to voluntary initiatives. Reducing the amount of waste produced, improving waste management practices, and increasing public awareness are all important steps in tackling marine litter (Martins et al., 2020). Representing the accumulation trends is also important to understand if the measures implemented are effectively reducing the quantity of marine litter. Beach surveys are the most common method selected for this purpose (Anastácio, 2015), but it is also important to understand the link between human behavior and marine litter typology and quantity.

The focus of this study is to understand the link between different socio-economic factors and the quantity and type of beach litter. Portugal was selected as a case study country due to data availability and a vast coastline vulnerable to the accumulation of litter and its impacts (Martins and Sobral, 2011).

As a Member State of the European Union, Portugal must comply with the MSFD (Directive, 2008/56/EC) and should monitor the quality

of coastal areas, which also includes the presence of marine litter (Prata et al., 2020). Following the requirements of the MSFD, there has been an increasing effort in monitoring and research programs through national agencies and research projects (Ghezzi et al., 2021). Frias et al. (2013), Velez (2017) and Guerrero-Meseguer et al. (2020) identified and characterized marine litter collected on beaches in the center, southern and northern regions of continental Portugal, respectively. Anastácio (2015) surveyed various beaches around Lisbon to link the sampled litter with the geological and local characteristics. Andriolo et al. (2020) and Gonçalves et al. (2020) developed a new framework based on unmanned aerial systems to detect marine litter accumulation on coastal dunes, testing it on beaches at the central Portuguese coast. In the Azores archipelago, Pieper et al. (2015, 2019) assessed the density, type, temporal trends, and sources of marine litter in two beaches of the Faial Island, Ríos et al. (2018) quantified and categorized marine litter found in 42 beaches, and Pham et al. (2020) demonstrated that insular environments, and particularly the Azores archipelago, are important transitory repositories of small plastics drifting in the ocean.

Few studies considered the entire Portuguese coastal region or, at least, samples distributed from north to south locations. Martins and Sobral (2011) identified the main size classes in stranded plastic debris from beaches' sediment; Antunes et al. (2013) investigated the occurrence of resin pellets and Prata et al. (2020) identified the highest concentrations of plastics in Portuguese beaches. All the presented studies have some limitations in the temporal distribution, only considering short periods of data. Only the work of Candeias (2015) tried to determine patterns of temporal and spatial trends in marine litter on the Portuguese coast using a 10-year (2001–2010) dataset distributed along the coast. But this analysis, in addition to being outdated, was limited to the data generated on a single project and excluded the archipelagos. It is clear that there are still important gaps and restricted spatial and temporal distributions in the research studies regarding marine litter on Portuguese beaches.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area

Portugal is a coastal country located in south-western Europe, with 1230 km of coast facing the Atlantic Ocean. This country also includes two archipelagos, Azores and Madeira, both in the Atlantic Ocean (Fig. 1a). Portugal is the 111th largest country in terms of area but has the 20th largest Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) with 1,727,408 km².

Portugal is divided into seven regions (North, Centre, Lisbon,

Fig. 1. a) Location of Portugal, its Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), and archipelagos (Azores and Madeira) (Adapted from SNIMar, <http://snimar.pt/>). b) Portugal subdivisions. Black lines represent the districts and grey lines the municipalities.

Alentejo, Algarve, Madeira, and Azores), according to the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistical Purposes (NUTS), in 18 districts, and in 308 municipalities, 278 at Portugal continental (50 municipalities at coastal area), 11 at the Madeira and 19 at the Azores archipelagos (Fig. 1b). The total population of Portugal was 10.31 million people in 2020, from which around 242,000 people live in the Azores (2.3 % of the Portuguese population) and 254,000 in the Madeira archipelago (2.5 %). Thus, the population is mostly concentrated in continental Portugal, especially in the coastal areas and in the two main metropolitan areas, Porto and Lisbon (Programa Nacional Para a Coesão Territorial, 2017). In Azores archipelago, the population is mostly concentrated in two of the nine islands: São Miguel, representing 57 % of the Azores population, and Terceira with 23 % (SREA, 2020). Both archipelagos have distinct coastal morphologies, lower population densities and industry. In continental Portugal, agriculture is mostly located in the North and Alentejo regions, industry in the North and Centre, tourism in the Algarve, and services and management in the metropolitan areas of Porto and Lisbon (Prata et al., 2020).

2.2. Data sources

The present study focuses on the beach litter found in continental Portugal and the Azores islands. The Madeira archipelago was left out of this study due to the lack of beach litter surveys in this area. The available data covers 19 municipalities in continental Portugal and seven in the Azores.

All the data recorded of beach litter in continental Portugal and the Azores islands were retrieved from the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet, 2023), which consists of homogenized

data from different sources, including EU Regional Sea Conventions, EU Member States, EMODnet partners, external research or monitoring projects, NGOs and citizen science, private companies and data from existing monitoring projects. The data for each survey included, among other information, the name of the beach, latitude and longitude, the date of the survey, and the type and number of beach litter items found in each survey. The minimum size of litter recorded was assumed to be 2.5 cm, at least for the data collected following European guidance (i.e., Galgani et al., 2013). Data for both types of surveys (100 m and 1000 m) was considered in this study. The period covered by the surveys ranged from 2002 to 2021, and a total of 454 surveys, 376 in continental Portugal and 78 in the Azores islands, were recorded (Table 1).

The socio-economic data was gathered from the two largest statistical databases from Portugal: Statistics Portugal (INE, 2023) and PORDATA (PORDATA, 2023). Different factors were chosen considering the basic information for each municipality (population, standard of living, labor market, etc.) and the variables that could be related to the production of litter (tourism, environment, ports, etc.). The availability of these variables for the study period (2002–2021) in a fair number of dates in the selected municipalities was also considered. Other relevant socio-economic indicators, such as waste generation and management, level of sanitation, and wastewater treatment could not be considered in this study due to the lack of data. Additionally, other categorical variables were considered, such as the presence of water masses (e.g., estuaries and lagoons) and ports, and if the municipality is located in continental Portugal or in an island. The final socio-economic variables considered are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1

Municipalities, continental Portugal and Azores location and number of surveys for each one of the beaches extracted from the EMODnet database.

	Beach	Municipality	Latitude	Longitude	Number of surveys (n = 454)	
Continental Portugal	Cabedelo	Viana do Castelo	41.673639	-8.826964	42	
	Barra	Ílhavo	40.640242	-8.748739	39	
	Batata	Lagos	37.097253	-8.667991	38	
	Ilha de Faro	Faro	37.002989	-7.9881	37	
	Amoeiras	Torres Vedras	39.125111	-9.390356	30	
	Monte Velho	Santiago do Cacém	38.081642	-8.811011	29	
	Oso da Baleia	Pombal	39.997856	-8.916519	29	
	Barranha	Póvoa de Varzim	41.454758	-8.779014	28	
	Paredes de Vitoria	Alcobaça	39.702786	-9.04995	13	
	Legua		39.653259	-9.069941	1	
	Baleal	Peniche	39.373419	-9.330928	11	
	Peniche		39.3588	-9.36316	1	
	Aberta-Pedrogao	Leiria	39.891333	-8.964722	10	
	Furadouro	Ovar	40.86548	-8.678148	9	
	Sao Pedro de Maceda		40.9329	-8.6601	2	
	Sao Felix da Marinha	Vila Nova de Gaia	41.030419	-8.646342	7	
	Cruz Quebrada	Oeiras	38.699603	-9.251834	3	
	Torre		38.675559	-9.323425	2	
	Paramos	Espinho	40.9857	-8.6475	2	
	Fonte da Telha	Almada	38.564586	-9.192556	31	
	Torrao		38.671841	-9.243079	2	
	Cabana do Pescador		38.60738	-9.21309	1	
	Costa de Caparica		38.631872	-9.229693	1	
	Moledo	Caminha	41.8495	-8.8665	2	
	Ancora		41.8074	-8.8647	2	
	Alges	Oeiras	38.696767	-9.231567	1	
	Novo Horizonte	Figueira da Foz	40.217467	-8.890067	1	
	Cabedelo		40.139948	-8.862221	1	
	Castelo do Queijo	Matosinhos	41.1742	-8.69041	1	
	Azores archipelago	Areia	Corvo	39.67249	-31.12118	14
		Almoxarife	Horta	38.55543	-28.61005	14
		Norte		38.60994	-28.75625	14
		Sao Lourenco	Vila do Porto	36.98847	-25.05488	13
Maia		Ribeira Grande	37.83302	-25.38632	12	
Pedreira		Vila Franca do Campo	37.71578	-25.464	8	
Vitoria		Vila da Praia da Vitória	38.7184	-27.061	1	
Flores		Santa Cruz das Flores	39.4749	-31.1483	1	
Porto Pim	Horta	38.524739	-28.625733	1		

Table 2
Socio-economic variables considered for the cluster computation and the questions that are intended to answer with this analysis.

Category	Socio-economic variable (unit)	Questions
Population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population density (N°/km²) 	Does more population imply more beach litter?
Standard of living	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purchasing power per capita (normalized to the country's purchasing power, it being designated by 100) 	Can higher power of consumption be associated with more beach litter? or Can a better standard of living be associated with regular cleanings and so less beach litter?
Labor market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People working in hotels, restaurants, and similar (%) • People working in agriculture, animal production, hunting, forestry, and fishing (%) • People working in manufacturing industries (%) • People working in construction (%) • People working in wholesale and retail trade (%) • People working in transport and storage (%) 	How does the prevalence of some sectors in the municipality affect beach litter?
Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gross enrolment ratio in basic education (%) • Gross enrolment ratio in secondary education (%) 	Is the level of education of the population conditioning beach litter?
Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overnight stays in hotels per 100 inhabitants (N°) 	Can more tourists be associated with more beach litter? or Can more tourists be associated with regular clean-ups, and so less beach litter?
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste collected separately (%) • Municipal environmental expenditures (€/1000 inhab.) in the domain of waste management • Municipal environmental expenditures (€/1000 inhab.) in the domain of protection and restoration of soil, groundwater, and surface water • Municipal environmental expenditures (€/1000 inhab.) in the domain of protection of biodiversity and landscape • Total municipal environmental expenditures (€/1000 inhab.) 	How does the allocated budget for the environment affect beach litter condition? And which domains have a higher impact?
Season	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Winter: December, January, February • Spring: March, April, May • Summer: June, July, August • Autumn: September, October, November 	Is there some seasonality in the beach litter? Is there more beach litter during tourist high season due to human activities? or Is there less beach litter during tourist high season due to more regular clean-ups?
Presence of water bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Categorical variable: yes or no 	Could water bodies increase beach litter, by transporting it from inland locations?
Presence of port Island	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Categorical variable: yes or no • Categorical variable: yes or no 	Could port activities increase beach litter? Does the geographical location affect beach litter due to, for example, different current patterns?

2.3. Methodology

The classification of the marine litter items from Portugal was downloaded from the EMODnet database and follows three different reference lists, namely the OSPAR reference list for 100 m surveys, the OSPAR reference list for 1000 m surveys, and TSG-ML (OSPAR, 2010; Galgani et al., 2013). The classification for this analysis was homogenized to the OSPAR reference list for 100 m surveys (Galgani et al., 2020). Items that did not match the OSPAR list were associated to a category that is as close as possible to the description and the material (Josse, 2021). The material of each category was attributed following OSPAR (2010), Galgani et al. (2013) and Fleet et al. (2021). The sources of each category were attributed following the Marine Conservation Society (2013) guideline. The full OSPAR reference list, the item's material, and sources, as well as the associations made for the non-matched categories are provided as Supplementary Material.

All the socio-economic variables were selected by seeking homogeneous data across the different sources. Nevertheless, in some cases, the information is not available for the entire study period (2001–2021). To complete the missing values, linear interpolations and extrapolations were used. If needed, conditioned values were left out to avoid unlikely estimations. For example, records corresponding to 2020 were not considered for the estimation of missing values due to the high influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on variables such as those characterizing the standard of living, the labor market, or the tourism sector.

2.4. Cluster analysis

After preparing the datasets, a PAM (Partitioning Around Medoids) clustering, also known as k-medoids clustering, was applied, in order to find the patterns associated with the socio-economic variables and the quantity and typology of marine litter. In this way, it is possible to infer about the local community's performance and establish some hypotheses that could help preventing beach litter. Considering each litter survey as an observation, the variables included in the cluster calculations were the socio-economic variables listed in Table 2 and the percentage of items found in that survey corresponding to each beach litter category.

The PAM cluster algorithm minimizes the distance between the points in their assigned cluster and the point designated to be the center of the cluster. This point, called medoid, is the data point in the cluster with a minimal average dissimilarity to all the other data points from this same cluster (Schubert and Rousseeuw, 2021). In other words, the medoid is the most centrally located data point in the cluster. There are several advantages of using the PAM algorithm: it is intuitive and less sensitive to noise and outliers compared to other algorithms like the k-means (Filaire, 2018).

In this study, the Gower distance was selected to measure the dissimilarity between observations (Gower, 1971). It is a common measure applied to clustering with mixed data, fitting well with PAM (Kaufman and Rousseeuw, 1990; Filaire, 2018). The Gower distance ranges between 0 and 1 and can be defined as the mean of variable-specific dissimilarities across observations, as represented by Eq. (1),

$$d_{ij} = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{f=1}^p d_{ij}^f \tag{1}$$

where d_{ij} is the dissimilarity between observations i and j , d_{ij}^f is a partial dissimilarity between i and j for variable f , and p is the number of variables. If f is a numerical variable, then d_{ij}^f is standardized using Eq. (2),

$$d_{ij}^f = \frac{|x_{if} - x_{jf}|}{R_f} \tag{2}$$

where x_{if} and x_{jf} are the observed values for the two individuals and the same variable f , and $R_f = |\max(n) - \min(n)|$ is the maximum observed

range from all individuals for variable f , being n the number of individuals in the dataset. If f is a categorical variable, the partial dissimilarity is equal to 0 only if observations x_{if} and x_{jf} belong to the same category, and to 1 otherwise. Missing values are allowed, as the dissimilarities for a given feature are computed considering only the non-missing values (Soares et al., 2021; Teixeira et al., 2023).

However, when using PAM, the number of clusters is not known a priori. The selection of the number of clusters to retain was made considering a balance between interpretability and cluster performance. In relation to interpretability, the selection of a low number of clusters may lead to uninformative results, while a high number of clusters can produce an over-segmentation, isolating small groups that cannot be considered representative of the general patterns (Soares et al., 2021; Teixeira et al., 2023). The cluster performance was evaluated using the silhouette coefficient, which indicates an optimal number of clusters based on the pairwise differences between and within cluster distances. This coefficient represents the contrast between the average distance between data points in the same cluster and the average distance to data points in the nearest cluster, which should be maximized (Filaire, 2018). Thus, to define the number of clusters for the PAM clustering, several iterations were made, starting with a number of clusters equal to 2 and using the *cluster* package of the software R (Maechler et al., 2022; R core team, 2018). Additionally, the cluster partitioning was depicted on a two-dimensional space using the *Rtsne* package in R (van der Maaten, 2015; van der Maaten and Hinton, 2008), which allows constructing a

low-dimensional embedding of high-dimensional data.

3. Results

3.1. Beach litter characterization

Fig. 2 shows the results of an initial beach litter characterization considering the material of the beach litter for each considered municipality. In general, the most abundant material considering all the municipalities was plastic, followed by paper, wood, and metal, which, summed over all the samples, correspond to a percentage of 92.9 % for plastic, 2.2 % for paper, 1.5 % for wood and 1.3 % for metal. Ribeira Grande municipality also presents an important amount of glass and pottery (Fig. 2b).

Regarding the sources of the litter (Fig. 3), considering all the municipalities, the results show that the majority of the items (46.5 %) cannot be attributed to a specific source (non-sourced). For the remainder items, the main source is public litter (34.5 % of total aggregated items), followed by fishing (9.8 %), sewage-related debris (6.4 %), and shipping (2.2 %). Ribeira Grande municipality also presents an important amount of fly-tipped litter (Fig. 3b).

It is important to notice that continental coastal regions exhibit distinct geophysical and geographical characteristics than remote oceanic coastal regions. Continental coastal regions are most affected by coastal nearshore-dynamics, while remote oceanic coastal regions are

Fig. 2. Percentages of litter material for each municipality a) at continental Portugal, b) at the Azores archipelago.

Fig. 3. Percentages of litter sources for each municipality a) at continental Portugal, b) at the Azores archipelago.

more influenced by large-scale oceanic circulation and dynamics (Pieper et al., 2019). For this reason, the top 10 beach litter categories were calculated for continental Portugal and Azores archipelago separately (Tables 3 and 4).

Only considering the top 10 categories of each region, it can be noticed that, for both regions, the top-three items found are plastic/polystyrene pieces with a size of 0–2.5 cm (OSPAR code: 117), cigarette butts (64) and plastic/polystyrene pieces with a size between 2.5 cm and 50 cm (46) (Tables 3 and 4). In both regions as well, the first category (OSPAR code 117) is overrepresented compared to the other ones. In continental Portugal, cigarette butts (64) and plastic/polystyrene pieces between 2.5 cm and 50 cm (46) are also much more prominent than the remaining litter, whereas, in the Azores, only cigarette butts (46) stand out compared to the others. Summed all over the samples and considering all the municipalities, the top 3 items percentages are 43.5 % for plastic/polystyrene pieces with a size of 0–2.5 cm (117), 30.1 % for cigarette butts (64) and 26.4 % for plastic/polystyrene pieces with a size between 2.5 cm and 50 cm (46). However, large differences arise if the analysis is made regarding the municipalities (Fig. 4). Considering that plastic/polystyrene pieces with a size of 0 cm to 2.5 cm (117) is the most prominent category, these items can be found in almost all the municipalities, except on Matosinhos, Figueira da Foz and Oeiras in continental Portugal (Fig. 4a), and Santa Cruz das Flores, and Vila da Praia da Vitoria on Azores (Fig. 4b). For the other municipalities, the most prominent category recorded were: cotton bud sticks (98) in Caminha,

Table 3
Top 10 beach litter categories (total items) at continental Portugal.

OSPAR code ^a	Litter categories	Material	Total Items	%
117	Plastic/polystyrene pieces 0–2.5 cm	Plastic/polystyrene	47,343	25.7
64	Cigarette butts	Plastic/polystyrene	33,497	18.2
46	Plastic/polystyrene pieces 2.5 cm > <50 cm	Plastic/polystyrene	30,330	16.5
98	Cotton bud sticks	Plastic/polystyrene	15,222	8.3
32	String and cord (diameter less than 1 cm)	Plastic/polystyrene	14,606	7.9
15	Caps/lids	Plastic/polystyrene	13,585	7.4
48	Other plastic/polystyrene items	Plastic/polystyrene	12,572	6.8
19	Crisp/sweet packets and lolly sticks	Plastic/polystyrene	7737	4.2
3	Small plastic bags	Plastic/polystyrene	4948	2.7
45	Foam sponge	Plastic/polystyrene	4491	2.4

^a OSPAR Commission (2010) Guideline for monitoring litter on the beaches in the OSPAR maritime area.

Table 4
Top 10 beach litter categories (total items) at the Azores archipelago.

OSPAR code ^a	Litter categories	Material	Total items	%
117	Plastic/polystyrene pieces 0–2.5 cm	Plastic/polystyrene	4910	39.8
64	Cigarette butts	Plastic/polystyrene	2734	22.2
46	Plastic/polystyrene pieces 2.5 cm > < 50 cm	Plastic/polystyrene	1347	10.9
48	Other plastic/polystyrene items	Plastic/polystyrene	1158	9.4
75	Other wood > 50 cm	Wood	470	3.8
32	String and cord (diameter < 1 cm)	Plastic/polystyrene	423	3.4
93	Other glass items	Glass	415	3.4
15	Caps/lids	Plastic/polystyrene	401	3.3
96	Other ceramic/pottery items	Pottery/ceramics	237	1.9
74	Other wood < 50 cm	Wood	230	1.9

^a OSPAR Commission (2010) Guideline for monitoring litter on the beaches in the OSPAR maritime area.

Póvoa de Varzim, Matosinhos, and Vila Nova de Gaia; plastic/polystyrene pieces between 2.5 cm and 50 cm (46) in Viana do Castelo, Espinho, Figueira da Foz, and Santa Cruz das Flores; cigarette butts (64) in Ílhavo, Oeiras, Almada, Santiago do Cacém, Lagos, Faro and Vila Praia da Vitoria; and other plastic/polystyrene items (48) in Vila Franca do Campo.

This analysis revealed strong differences in the litter material, source, and categories between the assessed municipalities. These differences could reflect the influence of different human activities, consumption and waste disposal behavior, and waste management, and could be associated with the variability of the socio-economic factors of

each region. This reveals the importance of establishing a relation between the socio-economic variables and the beach litter categories to find behavioral patterns and promote solutions to avoid these accumulations. To depict those differences, a cluster analysis was performed.

3.2. Cluster analysis

After running partitioning attempts from two to ten clusters using the PAM algorithm, seven clusters were retained based on the above-mentioned interpretability and cluster performance criteria. For seven clusters, the silhouette coefficient presented its maximum value (0.21). The centroids of the retained clusters are presented in Table 5. The centroid values for categorical variables (season, water masses, island, and port) represent the percentage of observations of each cluster belonging to each variable condition. It should be noted that some socio-economic variables did not present stronger differences between the clusters. These variables are the season, the gross enrolment ratio in basic and secondary education, and the percentage of people working in construction, wholesale and retail trade, and transport and storage (Table 5). Since the OSPAR classification is quite exhaustive, only the litter categories with a representation above 5 % in each cluster were considered in the analysis of results and included in Table 5. The centroids for all the variables and categories included in the PAM clustering are described in the Supplementary Material.

Fig. 5 shows the cluster partitioning displayed on a two-dimensional space. Each cluster’s observations are grouped approximately in the same zone of the plot, which highlights the relevance of the cluster partitioning. This is evidenced despite the fact that the dimension reduction carried out for this representation tends to produce some overlapping between points of different clusters, potentially making the clusters looking less cohesive (Soares et al., 2021; Teixeira et al., 2023). Additionally, the spatial cluster classification was included in Fig. 6. The cluster interpretation based on the obtained centroids is carried out

Fig. 4. Percentages of a) continental Portugal top 10 litter categories and b) Azores archipelago top 10 litter categories found in each municipality.

Table 5

Clusters centroids. Winter: December to February. Spring: March to May. Summer: June to August. Autumn: September to November.

Cluster		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Season	Winter	33	26	29	25	21	26	20
	Spring	29	20	27	42	24	29	27
	Summer	18	30	24	15	29	24	22
	Autumn	20	24	20	17	26	21	32
Water masses	No	0	93	0	100	0	0	0
	Yes	100	7	100	0	100	100	100
Island	No	100	93	100	7	100	100	100
	Yes	0	7	0	93	0	0	0
Port	No	4	100	0	100	100	100	0
	Yes	96	0	100	0	0	0	100
Population density		333	308	595	78	298	141	2599
Basic education		114	111	95	100	126	111	113
Secondary education		155	111	64	111	174	124	122
Purchasing power		92	91	87	84	133	93	115
Work at hotels		7	8	6	12	12	30	11
Work at agriculture		3	9	8	21	6	3	1
Work at industry		27	21	36	9	4	3	5
Work at construction		16	11	6	11	11	14	8
Work at trade		18	22	15	19	23	17	19
Work at transport		3	3	2	7	4	2	5
Hotels stays		212	287	130	612	656	3178	210
Waste separately		16	16	10	23	20	25	17
Expenditures in waste		2323	49,470	42,801	49,931	3178	101,967	56,408
Expenditures in soil		1437	58	202	125	97	0	19
Expenditures in biodiversity		24,050	8492	5175	2758	16,670	13,934	7429
Expenditures in environment		29,912	59,431	63,926	53,102	22,023	128,478	70,405
Litter categories	4	-	-	5.15	-	-	-	-
	Drinks	15	8.89	-	-	-	-	-
	Caps/lids	32	-	7.61	-	-	-	-
	String and cord	117	13.19	16.17	-	35.37	-	6.76
	Plastic pieces 0–2.5 cm	46	13.33	9.29	-	14.16	-	14.57
	Plastic pieces 2.5 cm > <50 cm	48	-	8.03	-	8.23	-	-
	Other plastic items	64	-	7.37	31.74	6.34	30.88	40.11
	Cigarette butts	98	5.45	-	-	-	-	10.9
	Cotton bud sticks	204	8.89	-	-	-	-	-
	Old cartons							

Fig. 5. Results of the cluster partitioning.

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of municipalities according to the prevailing cluster classification.

below.

3.2.1. Cluster 1: industrial 1

This cluster is an industrial cluster that comprises beach litter collection surveys performed in the northern area of continental Portugal (mostly in the Viana do Castelo municipality). The beaches included in this cluster are located near ports and coastal water bodies (estuaries). The mean population density in this cluster is medium-low, like its purchasing power and tourism activity. Due to its industrial activity, part of the municipal environmental expenditures is dedicated to soil/water protection and biodiversity, but the general expenses for the environment and waste treatment are low, and the percentage of waste collected separately is medium/low compared with the values of other clusters, which gives rise to a wide variety of beach litter typologies. It is one of the few clusters with cotton bud sticks and the only one with lids, but also the only one with neglectable quantities of cigarette butts, probably due to low tourism. However, there were found averaged quantities of plastics of various sizes.

3.2.2. Cluster 2: fishing

Cluster 2 is also an industrial cluster, but groups surveys that were mostly performed in municipalities that have neither big commercial ports nor large water bodies, such as Alcobaça, Espinho, Leiria, Ovar, Peniche, Pombal, Póvoa do Varzim, Ribeira Grande, Santiago do Cacém, and Torres Vedras. There is a prevalence of surveys performed in Northern and Central Portugal, and, as in cluster 1, mean population density and purchasing power are medium-low. It is a cluster with moderate tourism and plenty of industry, and with some agriculture/fishing activities, which differentiates it from cluster 1. The municipal environmental expenditures are generally low, particularly in the domain of protection and restoration of soil, groundwater, and surface water, and in the domain of protection of biodiversity and landscape. This is in agreement with the percentage of waste collected separately. It also translates into a variety of beach litter, including ropes, medium quantities of small- and medium-sized plastics (i.e., mesoplastics and

macrolitter), other plastic objects, and cigarette butts, although the latter were collected in lower quantities than in other cluster surveys. This is also the only cluster that presents a significant number of fragments, nets and cords from fishing activities. In fact, the municipalities prevailing in cluster 2 have a strong implantation of local/artisanal fishing.

It was mentioned by other authors that fishing-related litter can indicate deposition by the sea from fishing grounds because it is not expected to be disposed of directly on beaches but rather at sea or at fishing docks (Prevenios et al., 2018). In Portugal, local/artisanal fishing, also called polyvalent fishing, is the main fishing gear along the whole coastal region, including in the Azores archipelago (Lloret et al., 2018; INE, 2022). The fishing gear used is diverse but mainly comprises lines and nets. The vessels used for this polyvalent fishing represent around 80 % of the total fishing vessels in Portugal, with a considerable number of non-motorized vessels (INE, 2022). It is important to notice that the vessels for local fishing cannot go beyond the area of the captaincy to which they are attached, and they cannot navigate beyond the 6 miles. Therefore, the fishing-related items recorded on beaches likely originate from these near-shore activities.

3.2.3. Cluster 3: industrial 2

Cluster 3 represents the industrial cluster of the Aveiro region, namely through surveys performed around the municipality of Ílhavo. The population density is the highest among the non-metropolitan regions, but its purchasing power is lower than the other clusters, so, despite being more populated, this population is poorer. It is the cluster with the least number of overnight stays and therefore less tourism, and its economic activity revolves around the industry (the number of people working in manufacturing industries is the highest of all clusters), with no major agricultural/fishing activity. In this cluster, there are relatively high municipal expenditures allocated to waste management, protection and restoration of soil, groundwater, and surface water, although not so much in biodiversity protection and landscape. Additionally, the waste collected separately presents the lowest value of all the considered clusters. But, associated with the high value of total municipal environmental expenditures, there is little variability in the typology of beach litter; the only relevant items are drink packages (the only cluster that presents 5 % of this litter category) and cigarette butts (with the second highest percentage).

3.2.4. Cluster 4: islands

This cluster represents the municipalities located in the Azores archipelago, with the exception of Ribeira Grande, which, due to its fishing activities, was mostly included in cluster 2. Cluster 4 has neither ports nor water bodies, but the location of the islands in the middle of the Atlantic Ocean, and the complex patterns of marine currents that transport large quantities of material from different origins, must be taken into consideration. This cluster presents the lowest population density and purchasing power values. The tourism economic activities related to hotels/restaurants are relevant, but the main economic activity is agriculture/fishing, with practically no industry. In this cluster, there are some municipal expenditures dedicated to waste management, protection and restoration of soil, groundwater, and surface water, but low expenditures are dedicated to biodiversity protection and landscape. In general, the total environmental expenditures are average, but not sufficient to avoid the presence of beach litter. Small plastics from 0 cm to 2.5 cm (mesoplastics) are more abundant in this cluster, but there are also medium size plastics/macrolitter (i.e., sized between 2.5 cm and 50 cm), and other plastics. There are also cigarette butts, but the quantity is lower than for other clusters. This means that even though the rates of waste collected separately are high, there seems to be no relation between the amount of municipal environment expenditures and beach litter in this cluster. This could probably be explained by the prevalence of non-local litter sources. The large incidence of small items and fragments could be associated with the geographic position of these

municipalities, being subjected to the transport of marine litter from other remote locations, and not only due to waste generated in the archipelago.

3.2.5. Cluster 5: tourism 1

Cluster 5 represents beaches around the region's capital (Faro), with water bodies but without a commercial port. It has a medium population density but the highest purchasing power, influenced by a high number of foreign residents. Tourism is undoubtedly the main economic activity and it has some agriculture/fishing, but industry is residual. Not much public money is invested in waste management, although it presents a medium percentage of waste collected separately, and there are some municipal expenditures dedicated to the protection and restoration of soil, groundwater, and surface water. The highest amount of municipal environmental expenditures is allocated to the protection of biodiversity and landscape, although the total environmental expenditure is the lowest of all the analyzed clusters. Still, this is the cluster that presents the least variability of waste, as only cigarette butts are relevant, although in high quantity.

3.2.6. Cluster 6: tourism 2

This cluster represents one of the most touristic areas of the Algarve region, around the municipality of Lagos. In comparison, the percentage of workers in the tourism sector and the number of overnight stays is three to four times higher than in cluster 5. It has a low population density but medium purchasing power. There is a small agriculture/fishing activity and almost no industry. Due to the tourism activity, the total municipal environmental expenditure for waste management is the highest of all the clusters, in agreement with the quantity of waste collected separately. Not so much of the municipal expenditure is dedicated to the protection and restoration of soil, groundwater, and surface water (the lowest of all clusters), and to the protection of biodiversity and landscape (average value). But the care for the environment is reflected in the amount of beach litter, which has little variability (small plastics/mesoplastics and cigarette butts). It must be taken into account that this kind of beach litter are small pieces that are difficult to remove and to identify during beach cleaning. The cigarette butts, due to the intense tourist activity of this cluster, present the highest amount of all clusters.

3.2.7. Cluster 7: metropolitan

Cluster 7 represents the conditions of coastal metropolitan municipalities, especially those around Lisbon. Nearby the collection sites, there are large water bodies and ports. This cluster has the highest population density and a high purchasing power. Tourism, commerce and services are the main economic activities, and there are few industries and almost no agriculture. The municipal expenditures are more dedicated to waste management. However, the waste collected separately presents a medium/low value, which could be related to the high population density. In addition to the expenditures on waste, part of the municipal expenditure is also used for biodiversity and landscape protection. However, municipal expenditures for the protection and restoration of soil, groundwater, and surface water are low. The total municipal expenditures on environment issues are medium/high, but it does not seem to be enough for the high number of inhabitants. This cluster presents the highest quantities of medium plastics/macrolitter and cotton bud sticks, together with medium quantities of small plastics/mesoplastics and cigarette butts, in comparison with other clusters.

4. Discussion

During the last few decades, marine litter has gained interest due to its wide-ranging impacts on the environment and economic sectors. Reducing the quantity of litter that is found along the oceanic and coastal regions is considered imperative. However, tracing back the specific origin of marine litter and characterizing its sources remains

challenging and may hinder the prioritization of interventions.

Applied to several municipalities from continental Portugal and the Azores archipelago, this study intended to better establish the link between marine litter and socio-economic variables by applying a cluster analysis of beach litter surveys based on the PAM algorithm. The analysis was fed with parameters extracted from (i) official statistics databases (INE and PORDATA) to characterize socio-economic aspects related to population, education, the standard of living, labor market, tourism and environment, and (ii) datasets from EMODnet database on beach litter typology and quantity, collected between 2002 and 2021.

A first analysis of the beach litter characteristics revealed that, in general, the most abundant material was plastic, followed by paper, wood, and metal. The proportion of plastic found in the Portuguese coastline is in line with other regions in the North East Atlantic and in Europe, as presented by [Addamo et al. \(2017\)](#), who conducted a comprehensive analysis in several European regions, including north-western Spain, western Sweden, Bay of Biscay/Iberian coast, Celtic Sea, and the northern and southern regions of the North Sea, based on harmonized beach litter datasets reported to EMODnet. However, most of the plastic items found in Portugal correspond to fragments that result from a progressive degradation of larger plastics and cannot be recognized nor allocated to a specific source. As stated by [Prevenios et al. \(2018\)](#), such plastic pieces could not point to in situ littering activities but rather to sea or river-borne litter from distant sources. This remains one of the key challenges in determining the origin of this type of litter because physical phenomena such as waves, extreme meteorological conditions, and progressive abrasion transform large plastic objects into small pieces that are impossible to trace back. This further strengthens the need for studies that explore the relationships between the items found and the regional characteristics and activities that could explain their accumulation. Small plastic fragments (0 cm to 2.5 cm), or mesoplastics, belong to the top 10 categories of items found in practically all the analyzed municipalities in continental Portugal and the Azores, with the exception of Oeiras, Matosinhos, Figueira da Foz, Vila da Praia da Vitoria and Santa Cruz das Flores, where not small but medium plastic fragments (from 2.5 cm to 50 cm), or macrolitter, were found. This could be explained by the location of the beaches selected for sampling. In Oeiras, Matosinhos, and Figueira da Foz, the beaches are located close to ports and breakwaters or directly protected by the geometry of the coast, deflecting the main drift current and waves. In the Azorean municipalities of Vila da Praia da Vitoria and Santa Cruz das Flores, the sampled beaches are located in the south-eastern part of the corresponding islands, where the wave power is lower ([Matos et al., 2015](#)). A small number of surveys is also common to these municipalities, which could be hiding the variety of litter.

The cluster analysis also showed that plastic fragments are significantly more relevant in some regions, despite being present in almost all municipalities. As noticed by [Prata et al. \(2020\)](#), the Lisbon, North, and Centre regions showed the highest concentrations of plastics, in agreement with the results obtained in this study for clusters 1, 2 and 7. They pointed out that this could be related to high population density (especially in the Lisbon and Porto Metropolitan Areas) and to the industries in the North and Centre regions. However, the presence of these plastic fragments can also be explained by the strong dynamics, not only at the coast of continental Portugal but also at the Azores archipelago. The west coast of Portugal is highly dynamic, as demonstrated by the occurrence of diverse hydrodynamic processes. The prevailing northern direction winds on the western coast of the Iberian Peninsula produce dominant north-western waves with a mean significant height of 2 m and a peak period between 9 and 13 s ([Costa and Esteves, 2008](#); [Viitak et al., 2021](#)). Part of the energy of these waves feeds a southern drift current that can easily transport terrestrial materials from land to sea. In this region, freshwater discharges from rivers into the coastal ocean may cause a northward coastal countercurrent ([Peliz et al., 2002](#)), and river plumes may transport materials along the coast towards the open ocean ([Warrick et al., 2004](#)). Upwelling is often observed during the summer

months (May to September) when a narrow band of cold water is formed along the Portuguese coast, constraining the offshore transport of the buoyancy currents. During upwelling events, a succession of mesoscale structures can be seen, such as filaments, jets, meanders, ubiquitous eddies, and countercurrents (Fiúza et al., 1982; Serra and Ambar, 2002; Peliz et al., 2005). These features can spread zonally offshore up to around 200 km, acting as an important mechanism for the exchanges between the inner-shelf and the offshore regions (Sousa and Bricaud, 1992; Marchesiello et al., 2003; Relvas et al., 2007). Despite the strong dynamics observed in the Portuguese west coast, cluster 3 (Fig. 6) is not significantly influenced by the presence of small/medium plastics, as the sampled beaches are protected by the breakwaters of the Port of Aveiro, that, due to their orientation, deflect the main drift current and waves.

In the Algarve coast, and during the upwelling season, there is a recurrent warm countercurrent over the inner shelf that comes from the Gulf of Cadiz and surrounds Cape São Vicente. However, the dynamics in this coastal region are generally less energetic than in the Portuguese west coast, which may explain why small-to-medium plastic fragments are not relevant (below 5 %) in cluster 5.

The regional physical oceanography of the Azores archipelago is governed by the North Atlantic Subtropical Gyre, under the direct influence of the Gulf Stream. The Gulf Stream is then split into the North Atlantic Current, which flows in the direction of Northern Europe, and the Azores Current, which drifts south-westward and crosses the Mid-Atlantic Ridge south of the Azores archipelago (Käse and Siedler, 1982; Gould, 1985). All these currents, and their associated eddies, meanders, and filaments, are crucial in the oceanographic conditions of the Azores islands and in the transport, dispersion, and retention of material in this region. The topo-bathymetric configuration of the region also creates some specific and local currents, such as the one between the Faial and Pico islands, where strong currents and highly turbulent flows are created, but also generate the conditions to increase the capacity to capture and retain incoming material (Sala et al., 2013). These dynamics can lead to the accumulation of a significant amount of litter from remote regions in the Azorean beaches, so the reasonable municipal expenditures with the environment observed in cluster 4 are not enough to counteract this effect. This was already pointed out by Pieper et al. (2015, 2019), which concluded that the transport of marine litter around the Azores region associated with marine-based sources, such as coastal/ocean vessels and other large-scale sources, is related with long-distance processes, water column eddies mesoscale dynamics and near-shore/alongshore surface currents. Improper waste disposal on land, recreational activities, stormwater sewers and overflows, and other land-based sources present a very low contribution to the beach litter found in the Azores (Pieper et al., 2019).

In this study, data on recognizable litter items revealed that the main source is public litter, followed by fishing, sewage-related debris, and shipping. The top-three items found in continental Portugal and the Azores are plastic/polystyrene pieces with a size of 0 to 2.5 cm, cigarette butts, and plastic/polystyrene pieces with a size between 2.5 and 50 cm. In Addamo et al. (2017), the litter category that outstands above the others in almost all the represented regions is also related to plastic pieces, although with lower percentages than the ones found in Portugal (except for the North Sea). Besides the plastic pieces, the presence of cigarette butts and cotton bud sticks was also quite relevant in most of the regions analyzed by Addamo et al. (2017) but ranked differently from one region to another. Other litter categories in the top 10 rankings reported by Addamo et al. (2017) are different from the ones observed in Portugal and depend on the sea conditions and the socio-economic habits and activities of each country.

Generically, the cluster analysis indicated that low municipality environment expenditures, and, particularly in waste treatment, are linked to a large quantity and variety in beach litter typology. However, in clusters 4 (Islands) and 7 (Metropolitan), the municipal expenditures in environmental concerns are medium/high but do not seem enough to reduce the presence of marine litter at beaches. As previously

mentioned, in the former case this can be potentially associated to oceanic currents that transport a significant amount of marine litter from other locations. In the latter case, this may be explained by the high population levels and the fact that many of the surveyed sites correspond to urban beaches. As such, at least part of the recorded litter is likely to be generated by activities on the coast or surrounding areas. It was also possible to associate several beach litter categories with specific activities, such as ropes that were only found in the cluster that is more representative of locations with important fishing activities (cluster 2), and cigarette butts, more predominant in the tourism clusters (5 and 6).

There are, however, some limitations in the data used in this analysis. First, the retrieved beach litter surveys lack information regarding, for example, the number of participants and the duration of the surveys. Implemented by different institutions and organizations, and varying from well-structured scientific research and monitoring activities to voluntary clean-up actions and citizen science data, litter recording procedures may not be similar from one survey to another. At the same time, the sampling effort is not the same in terms of the number and periodicity of surveys across the different municipalities. A limited number of surveys can affect the representativeness of litter quantity and variety at a given location. However, it is very rare that a litter survey targets only specific litter categories. In this way, the promoting entity is unlikely to be a cause of bias of the percentage of items found in each category. Note that percentages, instead of the number of items, were used to avoid biased results caused by different timeframes and different resources used during the litter surveys.

The analysis here performed was limited to 26 out of the 80 coastal municipalities of Portugal. Additionally, during the high season, some of the sampled beaches may be subject to more frequent clean-ups, particularly in locations with tourism/recreation activities and with Blue Flag. The clean-ups may remove larger items and leave behind the smaller ones, as observed in cluster 6. However, the variable season was not discriminant between clusters, showing that there is not a large difference between summer, characterized by more tourism but also more clean-ups, and winter, characterized by less tourism and clean-ups but more prone to storms that can bring more litter to the beaches. Nevertheless, the data used are well distributed along the coastline of continental Portugal and across different islands of the Azores archipelago, being representative of different socio-economic patterns of the country.

Second, limitations can also be found in relation to socio-economic factors. Some variables that could improve the understanding of the relationship between beach litter and the local communities' environmental pressures (e.g., waste generation and management, water quality, and maritime transport) are not available at the municipal level or at least with the periodicity needed to perform reasonable estimations at the time of the litter collection surveys. However, some selected variables represent reasonable proxies for these effects (e.g., categorized environmental expenditures and the existence of ports and estuaries).

Despite the potential of cluster techniques to find association patterns between local/regional socio-economic factors and beach litter quantity and typology, the results do not necessarily imply the existence of a causal relationship. Also, the choice of including or not any specific variable in the analysis was subject to data constraints and conceptual considerations, but from the results, it is possible to observe if a variable is relevant or not for the partitioning.

In spite of the limitations, it should be stressed that the results presented in this work are coherent and well justified, strengthening the usefulness of the applied methods to explore the relation between beach litter and socio-economic indicators. In this way, the methodology can be easily transferable to support the challenging task of marine litter characterization in other regions.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a deep analysis of the beach litter on the Portuguese

coastline was performed, trying to establish a link between the quantity/typology of litter and human activities through several socio-economic variables, including population, education, standard of living, labor market, tourism, and environment. To accomplish this objective, a descriptive analysis regarding the typology, material, and sources of litter for each surveyed municipality, together with a clustering technique, was applied.

The initial analysis revealed that the most abundant litter material in Portugal is plastic, followed by a long distance by paper, wood, and metal. The main source, besides the non-sourced items, is public litter, followed by fishing, sewage-related debris, and shipping. The top-three litter categories are plastic/polystyrene pieces with a size of 0 cm to 2.5 cm, cigarette butts, and plastic/polystyrene pieces with a size between 2.5 cm and 50 cm. However, there is a strong heterogeneity between the surveyed beaches and municipalities. To explore these differences, a cluster analysis based on the PAM algorithm was implemented. This technique produced logical and reasonable results, despite data limitations. In this analysis, two industrial clusters, one fishing cluster, one insular cluster, two tourism clusters, and a metropolitan cluster were obtained. The analysis of these clusters revealed that, in general, low municipality environment expenditures, particularly in waste treatment, are linked with high quantities and a large variety of beach litter. Relationships between litter quantity and population density, but also oceanic transport in insular areas were also observed. Additionally, it was possible to find associations between beach litter quantity and typology with specific economic activities and geographic/hydrodynamic conditions.

Applied to Portugal as a case study, but easily applicable to other case studies/regions, the adopted methodology proved to be an effective tool that provides a better understanding of the socio-economic factors related to the levels and types of litter pollution. Moreover, the results obtained can support management measures based in real data.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115168>.

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